

Perceived Congruence Innovation :A Literature Review

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Abstract: Every company has its own way of increasing product sales every day. The goal of every company is to improve consumer purchasing decisions. One effective way that can be done by companies to improve consumer purchasing decisions is product innovation. Product innovation is the process of applying an idea or new ideas in order to produce new products that provide more benefits for users. There are various types of innovation, one of which is perceived innovation. Perceived innovation is an innovation that is formed according to what is felt by consumers. The idea of innovation can come from anywhere. One of the exciting ideas that can be carried out using perceived innovation is the theory of self-congruence. Self-congruence theory explains that consumers will consistently choose products that match their self-image. The purpose of this study is to find out new variables from combining two variables that have been proven to improve consumer purchasing decisions. Merging perceived innovation with self-congruence will obtain a variable or a new type of innovation which contains innovations perceived by consumers in accordance with their self-image which is called perceived congruence innovation.

Keywords: Innovation, Perceived Innovation, Self Image, Products, Self Congruence

I. INTRODUCTION

As the industrial world continues to grow, competition between companies is also getting tougher. Intense competition makes every company required to outperform other companies. If a company is unable to survive in the competition for consumers, it is certain that the company will go bankrupt and suffer losses (Ahn, 2022). Companies certainly try to compete by improving product quality. Companies are required to be able to provide new breakthroughs in order to improve product quality. The purpose of competition is to increase the quality of company products, namely to increase consumer purchasing decisions (Bodlaj&Čater, 2019). Consumers will see and compare the products of each company before deciding to buy the product. Purchasing decisions are a result of the decision-making process for each consumer to purchase a product that combines knowledge and information so that they can choose a product that suits consumers' wishes from several available products (Behnam et al., 2022).

One way to improve consumer purchasing decisions is to improve quality or develop products with innovation [Bianchi 2021]. Innovation has an important role in capturing the hearts of every consumer, so that consumers can be determined to choose these products (Aliasghar et al., 2022). Innovation can be very useful in increasing consumer buying interest because product innovations that are interesting and have been developed can become something new for consumers (D. Kim & Bae, 2020).

Innovation is a company mechanism for adapting to the times and the surrounding environment (Vuong et al., n.d.). Product innovation is the development and implementation of new ideas, the application of creative ideas and something new so that it can improve the appearance, benefits and objectives of the product, so that it can make the product one step ahead compared to competing products (Aliasghar et al., 2022). Without innovation, the company's products will be left behind by competitors' products because they cannot keep up with dynamic market needs (Chang et al., 2020). There is one type of innovation that is influenced by what is felt by consumers, namely perceived innovation. Perceived innovation is innovation that is felt, more like what consumers feel about the influence of the work environment or surroundings that can stimulate a supportive work environment (Manohar &Kapur, 2019).

One of the variables that can improve consumer purchasing decisions besides innovation is self-congruence (B. Y. Kim & Cho, 2022). Self congruence is the conformity of thoughts and self-concept that exist in consumers with an image formed by a company's products. A product certainly has its own concept or characteristics (Posts and

Telecommunications Institute of Technology, Vietnam et al., 2020). This can be used by consumers to measure how suitable they are with the product. With self-congruence, consumers will choose or buy a product or brand that matches the consumer's self-image so that a sense of image conformity arises (Kaur & Anand, 2021). Compatibility or alignment between consumers' self-image and the characteristics of a product can lead to consumer interest and purchasing decisions (Salimi&Khanlari, 2018).

From the previous explanations, it can be seen that consumer purchasing decisions can be influenced by two variables. The first is innovation, where the type of innovation used is perceived innovation which is an innovation that is felt or perceived by consumers (Ahn, 2022). The next variable is self-congruence which pays attention to the consumer's self-image [asdfghj]. By combining these two variables, it may be possible to create a breakthrough that can improve consumer purchasing decisions.

The purpose of this study is toelaboration a new variable which is a combination of perceived innovation and self-congruence. This new variable will contain innovations perceived by consumers in accordance with their self-image which is called perceived congruence innovation.

II. LITERATUREREVIEW

Consumer purchasing decisions are a final decision-making process taken by consumers about purchases that combine information and with certain considerations and comparisons (Deng et al., 2021). Decision-making by consumers in purchasing a product begins with the needs or desires of consumers. Purchase decisions made by consumers show how far the company is in capturing the hearts of consumers (Dettori et al., 2020).

Companies can use various ways to increase consumer interest in buying. One way to increase consumers is to use innovation (Turyahikayo et al., 2018). The demands of companies to be able to innovate on their products are very important so that the company's products remain the top choice for consumers. Product innovation is an alternative solution that can be used by companies to improve or enhance product quality so that they can always compete with competing companies and keep abreast of dynamic market needs. Innovation can also be a company strategy so that it can continue to exist in the product market (Su et al., 2018).

According to (Dr & Pretorius, n.d.) innovation is a process for creating new products, procedures, and new methods to create more value than previous products. Meanwhile (Behnam et al., 2022), argues that innovation provides gradual improvements to products, production, organizational systems, and marketing systems so that they can help consumers provide their value to products. Innovation is a company step in dealing with dynamic market needs and a place to apply the ideas obtained into existing products so that they can create old products that are already in great demand in the market with different sensations. There are six types of innovation according to (Aliasghar et al., 2022), namely new products, new services, new methods, new market development, new sources of supply, and new company organizational methods. Each type of innovation has a positive effect on company growth. This happens because companies are required to be able to make what consumers want to buy and are interested in. Consumers will always encourage companies to always innovate to issue products that are creative, unique and have advantages over other products [Omar 2021]. Consumers will also demand companies to be able to issue or create product innovations that suit their needs and desires (D. Kim & Bae, 2020). There is a type of innovation that is formed according to what is felt by consumers, namely perceived innovation (Ahn, 2022).

Consumer perceptions of product innovation can be divided into two perspectives, namely the producer's perspective and the consumer's perspective (Ahn, 2022). The producer's perspective will provide an overview of new products or products that have been combined with innovative ideas into the market (Deng et al., 2021). This will be based on the consumer's perspective which includes the characteristics of the new product, the risk of adoption, and the changes needed. According to (Chang et al., 2020) defining perceived innovation is innovation that shows new ideas and ideas for products that are considered potential and in accordance with what consumers feel. Something that is felt by consumers can be influenced by the surrounding environment. Perceived innovation has six indicators, namely perceived risk, complexity, compatibility, triability, observability, and relative advantage (Chang et al., 2020). With all the indicators that have been mentioned, perceived innovation can describe how consumers evaluate innovating products.

Companies can also improve purchasing decisions with self-congruence (Pramezwarly et al., 2021). For some people, self-concept is an important thing. Someone who considers self-concept as an important thing will direct or shape their behavior so that they can maintain and improve their self-concept (qwertyu). Self-concept is formed from an interaction process carried out by a person with the people around them, and these individuals try to improve

themselves according to their self-concept (Liu et al., 2022). Self-concept will be influenced by the product used (Laophon&Khamwon, n.d.). A product must also have a distinctive image of each company. The company will provide information and product characteristics, so that consumers will find it easier to find products that have a perception image in accordance with the consumer's self-concept [asdfgh]. Consumers will prefer products that have the most similar image to the consumer's self-concept (Wu et al., 2020). This results in consumers buying products that are in accordance with the consumer's self-concept, so that consumers have the means to express themselves (Abbasi et al., 2023). Consumers will evaluate the suitability of a product to be purchased in order to improve self-concept after seeing information about the product.

The image of a product can be obtained through the experience of using the product directly, word of mouth from consumers who have used the product, or information provided by the company on their platform [qwertyu]. Meanwhile, self-concept comes from a person's growth which causes the development of perceptions, attitudes, feelings, and evaluations of themselves (Xu (Rinka) & Pratt, 2018). (B. Y. Kim & Cho, 2022) states that purchasing decisions are influenced by the social value that consumers feel for product classes that are congruent or not with consumer social groups. (Suh et al., 2018) and (Sandhu et al., n.d.) suggest that consumers can position their consumption behavior to clarify their self-esteem. [asdfghjkl] explained that self-concept offers a useful perspective for understanding consumer decisions. Companies must be able to determine whether their products are relevant to improving consumer self-concept. In addition, companies must also determine the level of discrepancy between product image and self-concept which can reduce consumer purchasing decisions (Sahour& Dragomir, n.d.).

Self-image compatibility has been used in a lot of marketing to show that there is a match between two variables. [qwertyui] explains that self-congruence is part of self-image compatibility with product image, brand image, or company image. Products, suppliers and services are assumed to have a personal image of the company. The company's personal image can be described in how the company wants to be seen by consumers [qwertjkl]. Attributes in the company's personal image are related to products such as functional attributes which describe the product, as well as in terms of tangible costs and benefits such as quality, price, and performance (Suh et al., 2018).

Consumer perceptions of themselves will greatly influence their behavior in choosing a product as consumers (Pramezwarly et al., 2021). How consumers' perceptions of various product images and brand images will be influenced by their self-perception of consumers' self-image. The theory of product image conformity and self-image conformity states that the greater the suitability of a product and a brand, the more consumers will like it. (Japutra et al., 2019) Conformity is very likely to occur in several dimensions of a product to consumers' self-image. A product or brand may also not match its actual self-image, but may conform to its ideal self-image (Abbasi et al., 2023). The effect of conformity to self-image of consumers has been explained by self-conformity theory, this theory explains that consumer behavior will be determined by conformity resulting from psychological comparisons after consumers feel conformity with the product during use (Liu et al., 2022). The psychological level can be a comparison of how high or low the compatibility between the product and the consumer is. Self-congruence is high when consumers feel the product or brand image is in accordance with the consumer's self-image, and vice versa (Sahour& Dragomir, n.d.). Self-congruence greatly influences consumer behavior through consumer self-image such as the need for self-consistency and consumer self-esteem (Kaur & Anand, 2021). Therefore, product or brand image and self-image congruence greatly influence consumer purchasing decision preferences, ownership, use and loyalty to a particular product.

Table 1. PreviousResearch

Variable	Author	Year	Title	Result
Perceived Innovation	1. JiseonAhn	2022	Exploring perceived innovation in building customers' patronisingbehaviour in the food delivery service context	behaviour
	2. Mohsen Behnam, Vahid Delshab, dan	2022	Perceived service innovation in non-profit	This study has a sample of 578 non-profit sports clubs in Iran. The study

	LuuTrong Tuan.		sports clubs: the antecedents and consequence	results show that service innovation contributes to increasing the intention of actors.
	3. Quang Hung VUONG, SeyedMohammadreza GHADIRI, Thanh Tien NGUYEN	2022	Exploring Types Of Innovation, Customer Perceived Value, And Customer Satisfaction: A Literature Review And Hypotheses Development	The results of the research model strengthen the company's belief that customer-oriented management and the effectiveness of business operations through customer-perceived innovation for new changes.
	4. Omid Alisghar, Elizabeth L. Rose dan Kazuhiro Asakawa	2022	Sources of knowledge and process innovation: The moderating role of perceived competitive intensity	The sample of this research is 200 supplier companies operating in the Iranian automotive industry with 171 filled-out questionnaires. Companies are under pressure to systematically improve the efficiency of their manufacturing processes. The search for foreign knowledge is positively related to the innovation process.
	5. Christine Elena Bianchi, Gerson Tontini, Giancarlo Gomes	2021	Relationship between subjective well-being perceived organisational culture and individual profession to innovation	The sample data in this study were 614 professional workers in the business sector. This study shows that employee perceptions influence the innovation of each individual.
	6. Xiao Deng ,Xi Guo ,Yenchun Jim Wu dan Min Chen	2021	Deng, X., Guo, X., Wu, Y. J., & Chen, M. (2021). Perceived environmental dynamism promotes entrepreneurial team member's innovation: explanations based on the uncertainty reduction theory – international journal of environmental research and public health, 18(4), 2033.	By collecting questionnaires from 117 entrepreneurial team leaders and 479 team members in China, this study found that perceived environmental dynamism can stimulate entrepreneurial team members' innovation by triggering their information exchange behaviour.
	7. Nor Asiah Omar, Ahmad Sabri Kassim, Muhamad AzrinNazri, Noor HasniJuhdi	2021	The effect of retailer's perceived service innovation and value co-creation behaviour on SME's brand equity	The sample in this study was 529 questionnaires from SME customers involved in food and service. The results show that perceived service innovation positivelyrelates to SME brand equity.
	8. Angela Dettori, Michela Floris,	2020	Customer-perceived quality, innovation and tradition: some	This research follows the method of quantitative analysis. Data was collected from a sample of 200

	Cinzia Dessì		empirical evidence	consumers of Italian bread. The results show a negative relationship between customer-perceived quality and traditional product innovation in traditional industries.
	9. Daewon Kim, Jae Kwon Bae	2020	The effects of protection motivation and perceived innovation characteristics on innovation resistance and innovation acceptance in internet primary bank services	This study collected 398 online survey responses from non-users of internet primary bank services. As a result, there is a positive influence of protection motivation and innovation perception characteristics on innovation resistance and innovation acceptance.
	10. Chi-Cheng Chang, Chaoyun Liang & Yi-Chun Chiu	2020	Direct or indirect effects from “perceived characteristic of innovation” to “intention to pay	Participants in this study were 670 adult learners from an e-learning website. Questionnaires and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) were used to collect and analyse data. As a result, perceived innovation characteristics positively influence adult intentions to pay and continuing intentions to use e-learning websites.
	11. Mateja Bodlaj, Barbara Čater	2019	The impact of environmental turbulence on the perceived importance of innovation and innovativeness in SMEs	Structural equation modeling was carried out on 373 samples of SMEs. The research findings show that market and technology turbulence increases the perceived importance of innovation, but only market turbulence impacts SME innovation directly. Perceptions of innovation mediate the effect of environmental turbulence on firm innovation.
	12. Sridhar Manohar & Geeta Kapur	2019	Measuring perceived service innovation typologies in retail industry	This research follows the Integrated Design Approach which includes qualitative studies and quantitative studies in exploring and validating measurement items for service innovation typologies. The results of the analysis state that service perceived innovation has a positive impact on company reputation and WOM, where decision makers/managers can note that if service perceived innovation is often carried out, it will make the company famous in the market and ultimately generate positive WOM from customers.

	13. Ming-Feng Su, Kuo-Chih Cheng, Shao-Hsi Chung, Der-Fa Chen	2018	Innovation capability configuration and its influence on the relationship between perceived innovation requirement and organizational performance: Evidence from IT manufacturing companies	The research structural equation model was constructed and a questionnaire survey was conducted to collect data from research and development and production managers of IT manufacturing companies listed on the Taiwan Stock Exchange and Over-The-Counter market. As a result, the perceived need for innovation positively influences the configuration of innovation capability, which in turn improves organizational performance.
	14. Edison WazoelLubuaDr & Philip Pretorius	2018	The role of the transaction assurance, perceived cost and the perceived innovation in the decision to continue using mobile money services among small business owners	This study adopted a survey strategy, in which a closed questionnaire was used to extract data from 110 small business owners. In addition, this study adopts an ordinal regression model in making decisions about the proposed relationship through different hypotheses. As a result, transaction guarantees for perceived innovation and perceived innovation for the future significantly predict the intention to continue using mobile money services among small business owners.
	15. Turyahikayo, W.; Matsiko, F.B.; Okiror, J.J.; Obaa, B.B.; Hanf, J.H.	2018	The perceived role of innovation platforms in addressing the agricultural value chain collective problems: an empirical application of transaction cost theory	Using a randomly selected sample of 319 farmers from an innovation platform in Uganda, it was determined that uncertain markets for agricultural produce, sources of agricultural inputs and information were considered to be the main motivators for establishing the platform. The result is that the perceived innovation platform has no significant effect on the collective problems of the agricultural chain.
Self Congruence	1. Mitra Salimi& Amir Khanlari	2018	Congruence between self-concept and brand personality, its effect on brand emotional attachment	This study uses a questionnaire Designed and distributed among Parsian Bank customers and 380 usable questionnaires. The research method in this research is descriptive-correlation. This research has shown that brand personality consistency with consumer self-image has a positive effect on emotional attachment to

				the brand and the actual self-congruence effect is greater than ideal self-congruence.
2.	Jungmin Suh, Youseok Lee, dan Sang-Hoon Kim	2018	The effects of collaborated character's image congruence on cosmetic products evaluation: The relative importance of ideal and actual self-image congruence.	This study explores the effect of character collaboration on the evaluation of cosmetic products, focusing on the image alignment of the collaborating characters. This study reveals that consumers who perceive the collaborating character image as congruent with their ideal self-image have more positive product evaluations.
3.	Nayika Laophon& Anon Khamwon	2018	Self-Congruence, Emotional Brand Attachment, Brand Love, and Brand Advocacy: A Case of Fashion Brands	Data collection in this study was carried out using a questionnaire from 400 samples in Thailand. Then the data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). SEM results show that actual self and ideal self-congruence have an influence on emotional brand attachment, brand love, and brand advocacy.
4.	Sandhu, Moeed Ahmad; Usman, Muhammad; Ahmad, Zubair; Rizwan, Muhammad	2018	The impact of self-concept and its congruence with different brands on purchase intention: Evidence from Pakistani consumers	This study used a sample of 250 respondents analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM). The results verified the theory of self-alignment and recommended that better targeting is needed by understanding the self of the target market to be used in brand communication strategies. This study reveals that consumers evaluate brands by matching them with their self-perception (self-image) and hence develop attitudes towards brands that ultimately influence their purchase intentions i.e. those brands are preferred that match consumers' perceived self-image.
5.	Xu Xu& Stephen Pratt	2018	Social media influencers as endorsers to promote travel destinations: an application of self-congruence theory to the Chinese Generation Y	This study uses the self-congruity theory, which originally referred to harmony between consumers and brands or products, to harmony between endorsers and potential tourists to evaluate the effectiveness of endorsements.
6.	Chae-Man Na	2020	Relationships among sport-products self-congruence, product	The survey was conducted targeting 227 men & women in their twenties who are members of MTB, Tennis,

			love, product trust, and purchase behavior of sports-for-all club members	Badminton, Golf in 8 Seoul metropolitan areas. For the sampling method, convenience sampling method was used. The results of the study show that first, actual self-congruence has a positive effect on product love. Second, ideal self-congruence has no positive effect on product love. Third, social self-congruence has a positive effect on product love. Fourth, product love has a positive effect on product trust. Fifth, product trust has a positive effect on positive word of mouth. Sixth, product trust has a positive effect on repurchase intentions. Seventh, product trust has a positive effect on attitudinal loyalty.
7.	Shuhui Wu, Minglun Ren, Abdul Hameed Pitafi, and Tahir Islam	2020	Self-image congruence, functional congruence, and mobile app intention to use	The survey in this study collected 349 responses from Chinese smartphone users. The results of this study reveal that self-image alignment is significantly positively related to the intention to use mobile applications. Moreover, this research also shows that symbolic congruence is an important determinant of mobile app intention to use among Chinese smartphone users.
8.	Harsandaldeep Kaur & Sahiba Anand	2021	Actual versus ideal self: An examination of the impact of fashion self congruence on consumer's fashion consciousness and status consumption tendencies	This study used a sample of 751 millennials, this study confirms that ideal fashion self-congruence is a stronger predictor of status awareness and consumption compared to actual fashion self-congruence. In fact, fashion self-congruence actually does not have a significant impact on the two dependent variables. In addition, the results of the study also show that there is a mediating role of awareness between the relationship between self-ideal harmony and status consumption. This study shows several important implications for branded fashion apparel marketers by signaling the importance of the ideal self in the consumer decision-making process.
9.	Muhammad	2023	Self-Influencer	An online questionnaire was

	Nauman Abbasi, Aqsa Altaf, Nadir Munir Hassan & Nosheen Sarwat		Congruence: A Stimulus towards Purchase Intention	developed to collect data from 270 respondents who are members of fashion-related forums. The research hypothesis was tested using a structural equation model through Smart PLS. The findings reveal that self-congruence has a significant indirect relationship with purchase intention through the mediating effect of para-social interactions and perceived altruistic motives.
	10. Nguyen Thi Hoang Yen, Nguyen Thi Tuyet Mai		INTEGRATING THE THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR AND SELF-IMAGE CONGRUENCE THEORY TO EXPLAIN GREEN PRODUCT PURCHASE INTENTION	Data was collected through an online survey of 539 Vietnamese consumers. The results of data analysis using the structural equation model (SEM) show that actual self-image congruence has a direct positive effect on consumer intentions to buy environmentally friendly products. In addition, the findings suggest an indirect effect of actual self-image congruence alignment on purchase intention through attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control.
	11. Juliana, Amelda Pramezwaray, Delicia Natania, Annastasia Jessica Wirya, Gracia Kilisya Tasmalia, and Michelle Angel Darmawan	2021	Investigation Self Image Congruity and Restaurant Evaluation on Behavioural Intention Perspective Self Congruence Theory	Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to 136 respondents using convenience sampling. Statistical analysis is based on SmartPLS. Partial Least Square (PLS) path modeling is used to test the hypothesis. The results of the study show that the alignment of self-image and restaurant evaluation has a positive significance on behavioral intention. Restaurants are one of the most popular places for new hoteliers to start. This study has practical implications for designing successful marketing communications for various segments of Japanese restaurants based on customers' perceptions of self-image conformity.
	12. Hao Liu, Yu Mu, Xinhong Fu and Yuying Liu	2022	Passionately attached or properly matched? The effect of self congruence on grocery store loyalty	The findings indicate that lifestyle congruence has a greater mediating effect than emotional attachment in the relationship between store self-congruence and grocery store loyalty. Furthermore, social self-

				congruence is the dominant dimension of store self-congruence that influences grocery store loyalty
	13. Bo Yeong KIM & Erin Cho	2022	Effects of Self-congruence, Self-enhancement, and Delight on Tourists' Patronage Intentions, and Moderating Roles of Personality Propensities	The theoretical model of this research was developed using two theories, namely self-congruence theory and Hawkins Stern's impulsive buying theory. The first hypothesis discusses the effect of self-congruence on hedonic values, which shows a positive relationship between variables. Therefore, these results indicate that hedonic values such as fun, pleasure, happiness and the experience of joy are always associated with self-congruence. Furthermore, the relationship between self-congruence and customer satisfaction is examined as the most important variable that always influences customer satisfaction, with the conclusion that the presence of a self-congruence effect always gives high customer satisfaction.
	14. Arnold Japutra, YukselEkinci , Lyndon Simkin	2019	Self-congruence, brand attachment and compulsive buying	Based on a survey of 427 respondents, it is proven that self-alignment directly affects brand attachment, whereas actual self-alignment is a stronger predictor of brand attachment. Conformity between actual and ideal self does not directly influence obsessive-compulsive buying. This suggests that brand attachment fully mediates the relationship. However, actual self-alignment directly influences impulse buying but ideal self-alignment does not. This suggests that brand attachment partially mediates the relationship between actual self-congruence and impulsive buying and completely mediates the relationship between ideal self-congruence and impulsive buying
	15. Sid Ahmed SAHOUR, Anca Cristina DRAGOMIR	2018	THE IMPACT OF THE CONGRUENCE BETWEEN BRAND PERSONALITY AND SELF-IMAGE ON CONSUMERS'	The fit between brand personality and self congruence improves not only consumer satisfaction but also consumer-brand relationship. That is, when consumers perceive brand personalities according to their self-

			BEHAVIORAL RESPONSES: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	congruence, their satisfaction increases and the quality of consumer brand relationships improves
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From the existing exposure, the variable Perceived Innovation is obtained where the variable is the development of an innovation, where innovation itself is a company step in dealing with dynamic market needs and a container for applying ideas obtained into existing products so that they can create old products that are there are already many enthusiasts in the market with different sensations (Ahn, 2022). So that from this development it is known that Perceived Innovation is an innovation that shows new ideas and ideas for products that are considered potential and in accordance with what consumers feel (Chang et al., 2020). In addition, one variable that is also very important is the variable Self Congruence where in the literature it is stated that Self Congruence is the consumer's perception of using products that have appropriate attributes or can consistently support their self-concept (B. Y. Kim & Cho, 2022). By obtaining the two variables that have been stated above, a new variable is obtained, namely perceived congruence innovation where this variable is a combination of the Perceived Innovation variable and the Self Congruence variable. Because it is formed from two variables, the perceived congruence innovation variable is an innovation that is perceived by consumers according to their self-image.

III. CONCLUSION

The conclusion in this study is that a new variable can be formed by combining two variables that can improve consumer purchasing decisions. The two variables are perceived innovation and self-congruence. Perceived innovation is an innovation that is formed according to what is felt by consumers. Meanwhile, self-congruence is a theory that explains that consumers will consistently choose products that match their self-image. From previous research, it can be concluded that these two variables have a positive influence on consumer purchasing decisions. Therefore, the combination of these two variables will create a new variable that is very possible to significantly increase consumer purchasing decisions. The combined variable of perceived innovation and self-congruence is perceived congruence innovation. Perceived congruence innovation is an innovation that is perceived by consumers according to their self-image, so that they can meet the needs and desires of consumers who tend to conform to their self-image.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abbasi, M. N., Altaf, A., Hassan, N. M., & Sarwat, N. (2023). Self-Influencer Congruence: A Stimulus towards Purchase Intention. *Review of Education, Administration & Law*, 6(1), 13-30. <https://doi.org/10.47067/real.v6i1.291>
- [2] Ahn, J. (2022). Exploring perceived innovation in building customers' patronizing behavior in the food delivery service context. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 14(2), 258-273. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQSS-08-2021-0114>
- [3] Aliasghar, O., Rose, E. L., & Asakawa, K. (2022). Sources of knowledge and process innovation: The moderating role of perceived competitive intensity. *International Business Review*, 31(2), 101920. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2021.101920>
- [4] Behnam, M., Delshab, V., & Tuan, L. T. (2022). Perceived service innovation in non-profit sports clubs: The antecedents and consequence. *European Sport Management Quarterly*, 22(3), 440-462. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16184742.2020.1799051>
- [5] Bodlaj, M., & Cater, B. (2019). The Impact of Environmental Turbulence on the Perceived Importance of Innovation and Innovativeness in SMEs. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 57(sup2), 417-435. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsbm.12482>
- [6] Chang, C.-C., Liang, C., & Chiu, Y.-C. (2020). Direct or indirect effects from "perceived characteristic of innovation" to "intention to pay": Mediation of continuance intention to use e-learning. *Journal of Computers in Education*, 7(4), 511-530. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-020-00165-6>
- [7] Deng, X., Guo, X., Wu, Y. J., & Chen, M. (2021). Perceived Environmental Dynamism Promotes Entrepreneurial Team Member's Innovation: Explanations Based on the Uncertainty Reduction Theory. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(4), 2033. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18042033>
- [8] Dettori, A., Floris, M., & Dessì, C. (2020). Customer-perceived quality, innovation and tradition: Some empirical evidence. *The TQM Journal*, 32(6), 1467-1486. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-11-2019-0273>
- [9] Dr, E. W. L., & Pretorius, P. (n.d.). *The role of the transaction assurance, perceived cost and the perceived innovation in the decision to continue using mobile money services among small business owners*. 10(2).

- [10] Japutra, A., Ekinci, Y., & Simkin, L. (2019). Self-congruence, brand attachment and compulsive buying. *Journal of Business Research*, 99, 456–463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.08.024>
- [11] Kaur, H., & Anand, S. (2021). Actual versus ideal self: An examination of the impact of fashion self congruence on consumer's fashion consciousness and status consumption tendencies. *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing*, 12(2), 146–160. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20932685.2020.1856705>
- [12] Kim, B. Y., & Cho, E. (2022). Effects of Self-congruence, Self-enhancement, and Delight on Tourists' Patronage Intentions, and Moderating Roles of Personality Propensities. *International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15256480.2021.2025188>
- [13] Kim, D., & Bae, J. K. (2020). The Effects of Protection Motivation and Perceived Innovation Characteristics on Innovation Resistance and Innovation Acceptance in Internet Primary Bank Services. *GLOBAL BUSINESS FINANCE REVIEW*, 25(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.17549/gbfr.2020.25.1.1>
- [14] Laophon, N., & Khamwon, A. (n.d.). SELF-CONGRUENCE, EMOTIONAL BRAND ATTACHMENT, BRAND LOVE, AND BRAND ADVOCACY: A CASE OF FASHION BRANDS. 4(11).
- [15] Liu, H., Mu, Y., Fu, X., & Liu, Y. (2022). Passionately attached or properly matched? The effect of self-congruence on grocery store loyalty. *British Food Journal*, 124(11), 4054–4071. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-08-2021-0848>
- [16] Manohar, S., & Kapur, G. (2019). Measuring Perceived Service Innovation Typologies in Retail Industry. *Journal of Industrial Integration and Management*, 04(02), 1850019. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2424862218500197>
- [17] Posts and Telecommunications Institute of Technology, Vietnam, Yen, N. T. H., Mai, N. T. T., & National Economics University, Vietnam. (2020). Integrating the Theory of Planned Behavior and SelfImage Congruence Theory to Explain Green Product Purchase Intention. *International Journal of Marketing and Social Policy*, 2(1), 2–11. <https://doi.org/10.17501/23621044.2019.2102>
- [18] Pramezwar, A., Natania, D., Wirya, A. J., Tasmalia, K., & Darmawan, M. A. (2021). Investigation Self Image Congruity and Restaurant Evaluation on Behavioural Intention Perspective Self Congruence Theory. 5(1).
- [19] Sahour, S. A., & Dragomir, A. C. (n.d.). THE IMPACT OF THE CONGRUENCE BETWEEN BRAND PERSONALITY AND SELF-IMAGE ON CONSUMERS' BEHAVIORAL RESPONSES: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK. 7(3).
- [20] Salimi, M., & Khanlari, A. (2018). CONGRUENCE BETWEEN SELF-CONCEPT AND BRAND PERSONALITY, ITS EFFECT ON BRAND EMOTIONAL ATTACHMENT. 22(4).
- [21] Sandhu, M. A., Usman, M., Ahmad, Z., & Rizwan, M. (n.d.). The impact of self-concept and its congruence with different brands on purchase intention: Evidence from Pakistani consumers.
- [22] Su, M.-F., Cheng, K.-C., Chung, S.-H., & Chen, D.-F. (2018). Innovation capability configuration and its influence on the relationship between perceived innovation requirement and organizational performance: Evidence from IT manufacturing companies. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 29(8), 1316–1331. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMTM-03-2018-0097>
- [23] Suh, J., Lee, Y., & Kim, S.-H. (2018). The effects of collaborated character's image congruence on cosmetic products evaluation: The relative importance of ideal and actual self-image congruence. *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing*, 9(2), 103–115. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20932685.2018.1426482>
- [24] Turyahikayo, W., Matsiko, F., Okiror, J., Obaa, B., & Hanf, J. (2018). The perceived role of innovation platforms in addressing the agricultural value chain collective problems: An empirical application of transaction cost theory. *International Journal of Agricultural Research, Innovation and Technology*, 8(2), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3329/ijarit.v8i2.40550>
- [25] Vuong, Q. H., Ghadiri, S. M., & Nguyen, T. T. (n.d.). EXPLORING TYPES OF INNOVATION, CUSTOMER PERCEIVED VALUE, AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION: A LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT.
- [26] Wu, S., Ren, M., Pitafi, A. H., & Islam, T. (2020). Self-Image Congruence, Functional Congruence, and Mobile App Intention to Use. *Mobile Information Systems*, 2020, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/5125238>
- [27] Xu (Rinka), X., & Pratt, S. (2018). Social media influencers as endorsers to promote travel destinations: An application of self-congruence theory to the Chinese Generation Y. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 35(7), 958–972. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10548408.2018.1468851>